

The F_1 means deviated conspicuously from parental and mid-parental values, indicating nonadditive gene action for these two characters. Substantial heterosis in the desirable direction was observed in IVB and OVB, which are related to higher numbers of primary branches.

The table shows the mean value for four selected crosses and their parents. All the crosses had 25 or more IVB, compared to 17.7 for the parental mean. They also exhibited positive heterosis and heterobeltiosis. Most of the crosses had positive heterosis and negative heterobeltiosis for OVB, CD, and MC, but both estimates were negative for CT. Rewa 353-2/IR30 showed positive heterosis and heterobeltiosis for all characters except CT.

The potence ratio indicated overdominance for IVB, OVB, CD, and MD and partial dominance for CT. □

Mean values of 5 panicle characters in selected hybrids and their parents, percentage of heterosis and heterobeltiosis, and estimates of potence ratio. IRR, 1989.

Parent or cross	Inner vascular bundle (no.)		Outer vascular bundle (no.)		Culm diameter (mm)	Medullary cavity (mm)		Culm thickness (mm)		
	H	Hb	H	Hb		H	Hb	H	Hb	
IR30	(1)	18.3	18.9		2.08		1.51		0.28	
IR29692-117-1-2-2	(2)	16.4	20.2		2.00		1.29		0.35	
IR28211-43-1-1-2	(3)	20.5	24.9		2.32		1.68		0.32	
IR29429-13-3-13-1-3	(4)	20.4	21.8		2.72		2.06		0.33	
IR47705-AC5-1	(5)	21.0	31.8		2.65		1.81		0.42	
IR47705-AC5	(6)	22.8	30.4		2.71		1.91		0.40	
Rewa 353-2	(7)	20.1	20.0		2.37		1.76		0.30	
IR36 (check)		15.1	17.6		1.72		1.21		0.26	
Mean		19.3	23.2		2.32		1.65		0.34	
Mean (over 34 parents)		17.7	22.5		2.21		1.50		0.35	
LSD (0.05)		1.5	2.2		0.15		0.14		0.03	
Cross:										
6 × 2		25.4	28.3		2.54		1.83		0.36	
5 × 4		25.0	28.2		2.69		2.00		0.34	
5 × 3		25.7	30.5		2.52		1.80		0.36	
7 × 1		25.2	23.1		2.46		1.86		0.30	
Mean		25.3	27.5		2.55		1.87		0.34	
Mean (over 43 crosses)		19.0	23.2		2.26		1.60		0.33	
LSD (0.05)		1.5	1.5		0.10		0.09		0.02	
Heterosis (H) and Heterobeltiosis (Hb)	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb	H	Hb
6 × 2	29.6	11.4	11.9	-6.9	8.2	-6.1	14.4	-4.1	-7.9	-15.2
5 × 4	20.7	19.1	5.3	-11.3	0.2	-1.1	3.2	-3.1	-10.6	-20.3
5 × 3	23.9	22.4	7.6	-4.1	1.3	-4.9	3.5	-0.3	-4.2	-15.0
7 × 1	31.1	22.2	18.8	15.5	10.6	3.9	13.8	5.6	1.4	-1.7
LSD (0.05)	2.1	2.2	2.6	5.1	2.2	1.9	2.7	1.9	2.2	3.5
Potence ratio										
6 × 2		-19.3		-25.2		-2.3		-1.5		-0.5
5 × 4		-20.5		-26.7		-2.7		-1.9		-0.5
5 × 3		-20.5		-28.3		-2.5		-1.7		-0.4
7 × 1		-18.9		-19.3		-2.1		-1.5		-0.3

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Grain quality and nutritional value

Inheritance of grain length, width, thickness, and weight in Pakistan Basmati/IR1469 and Pakistan Basmati/Paizam 242

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Parents, F_1 s, and F_2 s (500 plants each) were raised during 1988 wet season at CRR, Cuttack. Mature panicles were collected from individual plants. Three seeds from each plant were measured for grain length, width, and thickness. Hundred-grain weight was recorded.

In Pakistan Basmati/IR1469, F_1 grain length, width, and thickness were around the mid-parent value; F_2

maximum frequencies were around the mean (Table 1). Grain width showed overdominance in the F_1 and F_2 . In P. Basmati/Paizam 242, maximum frequency for grain length was around

Table 1. Means for grain length, width, thickness, grain weight of P. Basmati/IR1469 and P. Basmati, Paizam 242. CRR, India, 1988 wet season.

Cross characters	Parents		F_1 s	F_2 s					
	P ₁	P ₂		Mean	Range	Variance	SE	CV (%)	
<i>P. Basmati/IR1469</i>	<i>P. Basmati</i>	<i>IR1469</i>							
Grain length (mm)	11.42	8.67	10.00	9.88	8.10 - 12.38	5601.3	3.34	7.5	
Grain width (mm)	2.26	3.00	2.79	2.69	2.02 - 3.05	351.7	0.84	6.9	
Grain thickness (mm)	1.91	2.11	2.06	2.02	1.73 - 2.23	65.5	0.36	4.0	
100-grain weight (g)	2.38	2.68	2.77	2.64	1.40 - 3.80	14.9	0.17	1.4	
<i>P. Basmati/Paizam 242</i>	<i>P. Basmati</i>	<i>Paizam 242</i>							
Grain length (mm)	11.42	7.51	9.04	9.04	7.61 - 11.41	4311.0	2.91	7.2	
Grain width (mm)	2.26	2.57	2.52	2.43	2.05 - 2.80	227.4	0.67	6.2	
Grain thickness (mm)	1.91	1.85	1.92	1.88	1.58 - 2.06	55.8	0.33	3.9	
100-grain weight (g)	2.38	1.64	2.12	2.03	1.25 - 2.85	910.4	3.96	14.8	

the mean. F_1 values for grain width, thickness, and weight were higher than in the mid-parent; F_2 values were toward the high parent.

Path coefficients showing direct and indirect effects of grain length, width, and thickness on grain weight and total correlations are presented in Table 2. There were no significant correlations among grain length, width, thickness, and weight in parents P. Basmati and IR1469. In Paizam 242, the association between length and thickness was positive, that between thickness and weight was negative. In P. Basmati, the direct effect of grain length on weight was positive and independent of indirect effects. In IR1469, the direct effect of grain length was negative and independent of indirect effects. In Paizam 242, the direct effect of thickness was negative and its indirect effect on grain length was high.

In the F_1 of P. Basmati/IR1469, the associations among length and width and grain weight were positive. The high direct effect of width was influenced to some extent by the negative effect of grain length. In the F_1 of P. Basmat/Paizam 242, there were no significant associations among the four characters.

Correlations in F_2 populations showed similar trends. Associations

Table 2. Path coefficients for components of 100-grain weight. CRRI, India, 1988.

Influence and association	Parents			F_1		F_2	
	Pakistan Basmati	IR1469	Paizam 242	Pakistan Basmati/IR1469	Pakistan Basmati/Paizam 242	Pakistan Basmati/IR1469	Pakistan Basmati/Paizam 242
<i>100-grain weight vs grain length</i>							
Direct effect	0.3805	-0.7134	0.1822	-0.2860	0.1434	0.4876	0.3636
Indirect effect via grain width	0.0913	0.0838	0.0088	0.7195	0.2372	-0.0314	-0.0155
Indirect effect via thickness	-0.0250	0.0949	-0.6349	0.0977	-0.0572	0.0664	0.0903
Total correlation	0.4468	-0.5347	-0.4439	0.5312	0.3234	0.5226**	0.4384**
<i>100-grain weight vs grain width</i>							
Direct effect	0.2269	0.2260	0.0915	0.8342	0.4997	0.4097	0.3262
Indirect effect via grain length	0.1531	-0.2645	0.0176	-0.2466	0.0681	-0.0374	-0.0172
Indirect effect via grain thickness	-0.0116	0.1087	0.0850	0.0855	-0.0370	0.1592	0.1795
Total correlation	0.3684	0.0702	0.1941	0.6731**	0.5308	0.5315**	0.4885**
<i>100-grain weight vs grain thickness</i>							
Direct effect	-0.0807	-0.3531	-0.7598	0.1789	-0.2148	0.2451	0.3178
Indirect effect via grain length	0.1177	0.1917	0.1522	-0.1563	0.0382	0.1321	0.1033
Indirect effect via grain width	0.0325	-0.0696	-0.0102	0.3989	0.0861	0.2661	0.1843
Total correlation	0.0695	-0.2310	-0.6178**	0.4215	-0.0905	0.6433**	0.6054**

among all characters except grain length and width were positive. The direct effects of grain length and width were positive. The direct effect of grain length and width on weight were equal. The direct effect of grain length was independent of indirect effects. Grain width was influenced by the indirect effect of grain thickness. The direct effect of grain thickness was due primarily to the indirect effects of grain

length and grain width.

Inheritance of grain length and width were found to be independent and governed by different sets of genes. Grain thickness depends on the correlation of length and width. With the independent action of length and width, grain weight can exceed both parents. Inheritance patterns of grain dimensions are useful in breeding for a specific grain type. □

Disease resistance

Disease resistance in Chinese hybrid rices

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More than 10 new hybrid rices are developed in China each year. Breeders have been focusing on yield characters. We report on the disease resistance of the hybrid rices involved in the 1987-88 regional test in South China and Jiangxi Province.

Pyricularia oryzae mixed with many monoconidial isolates from Jiangxi (suspension = 50-60 conidial 100 parts) was spray inoculated at the seedling stage. *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* from highly virulent group XII was inoculated by

cutting flag leaves during heading. We also evaluated the incidence of blast (Bl), bacterial blight (BB), sheath blight (ShB), and false smut (FS).

More of 87 hybrid cultivars tested in 1987 and 1988 were resistant to Bl than to BB (see table). Cultivar

Distribution, by resistance, of hybrid rices tested in Jiangxi, China, 1987-88.

Year	Disease	Cultivars showing given disease reaction										Cultivars (no.)	Resistant cultivars (%)
		R		MR		MS		S		HS			
		no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%		
1987	Bl	4	8.7	15	32.6	19	41.3	5	10.9	3	6.5	46	41.3
	BB	2	4.4	5	11.1	12	26.7	8	17.8	18	40.0	45	15.5
1988	Bl	20	52.6	9	23.7	5	13.2	4	10.5	0	0	38	76.3
	BB	1	2.4	2	4.8	1	2.4	9	21.4	29	69.1	42	7.0